

A Novel Approach Of SHA-512 Integration with BeDD For Safe And Effective Data Management In Mec

Dr. Rishi Sayal¹, Pooja Kulkarni², Harshavardhan Ravilla³, Disha Jhun Jhun Wala⁴
Guru Nanak Institutions Technical Campus^{1,2,3,4}, Hyderabad^{1,2,3,4}
ad.rs@gniindia.org¹, kulkarni.pooja.26@gmail.com²,
harshavardhan76740@gmail.com³, dishajhunjhunwala6333@gmail.com⁴

Abstract

Data creation from mobile devices and edge sensors has increased at an unprecedented rate due to the rise of data-intensive apps and the Internet of Things (IoT). Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) has emerged as a viable paradigm to extend cloud computing capabilities to the network edge and satisfy the low-latency needs of these applications. But the speed and scalability of edge-hosted applications are severely hampered by the small storage capacity of edge servers. In this paper, we propose to integrate the already-existing Balanced Edge Data Deduplication (BEDD)[1] with SHA-512. This is a novel approach to transforming edge devices into compute environments through extensive experiments on real-world datasets. The solution optimizes data storage and resource utilization in the MEC environments through intelligent data deduplication which show how much better BEDD is than current techniques, saving storage costs and preserving data security with SHA-512 incorporation.

Keywords: MEC, Data Deduplication, Edge Compute, SHA-512, Storage Optimization

I. Introduction

Data creation at the network edge has increased at an unprecedented rate due to the widespread use of mobile devices and the quick spread of the Internet of Things (IoT). Traditional cloud computing infrastructures have been put under strain by this data flood as well as the growing need for low-latency applications like augmented reality, driverless cars, and real-time analytics. The concept of Mobile Edge Computing (MEC), which extends cloud computing capabilities to the network edge, has shown promise in addressing these issues [2].

Fig. 1. Edge Storage System

In MEC, processing and storage resources may be moved closer to end users and data sources by deploying edge servers at base stations or access points. Because of this close proximity, low-latency service delivery is made easier, network congestion is decreased, and system performance is enhanced overall. However, because of their reduced physical footprint, edge servers usually have limited storage capacity, which presents serious difficulties for data-intensive applications hosted on the edge [3]. Although there has been much research on data deduplication strategies in cloud storage systems to reduce redundancy and maximize storage efficiency, these methods frequently ignore the special qualities of MEC contexts. In particular, latency limitations, the geographical dispersion of edge servers, and the diversity of data access patterns and storage needs among various edge locations are all factors that MEC systems need to take into account [4].

Fig. 2. BEDD solutions with the same deduplication and Cryptography

In order to address these issues, we propose the Balanced Edge Data Deduplication (BEDD) method, which is currently in use. By utilizing intelligent data deduplication, BEDD optimizes data storage and resource utilization in MEC environments. Additionally, BEDD integrates with SHA-512, a reliable cryptographic hash function from the Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA) family, to guarantee data integrity, authentication, and security against malicious attacks [5].

The remainder of the document is structured as follows: Section II examines relevant research on data deduplication methods and their drawbacks in mobile edge computing settings, While Section III describes the proposed system, it also includes a thorough use case scenario, an analysis of storage utilization, load balancing, and security aspects, and details about the current Balanced Edge Data Deduplication (BEDD) algorithm and its integration with the SHA-512 cryptographic hash function for enhanced security. The performance evaluation findings are covered in Section IV, along with a comparison of the suggested solution with current practices and an emphasis on its benefits for attaining safe and balanced data management. Section V examines how the suggested methodology may be improved in the future, including through dynamic adaptation, integration with frameworks for collaborative edge computing, and the use of sophisticated security measures. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper, summarizing the key contributions and the benefits of the BeSHA-1 solution in enabling safe and effective data management in mobile edge computing environments.

II. Related work

Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) allows popular data to be cached on edge servers close to users' locations, so addressing the inadequacies of cloud computing in providing low latency services (Xiaoyu Xia, Fei-Fei Chen, Qiang He, et al., 2016). However, edge servers have restricted storage capacity because of their small physical footprint. The majority of research on edge caching has been on improving caching performance for mobile network operators, which includes balancing caching workloads, increasing data retrieval success rates, and lowering system energy usage [6][7].

But as important participants in MEC systems, app providers also need to prioritize improving caching revenue while weighing the advantages and disadvantages. We present Online MEDC (OL-MEDC), an approach that generates MEDC strategies for app developers without needing them to know what data needs they may have in the future. Its efficacy is assessed both philosophically and empirically. Based on experimental data, OL-MEDC performs at least 20.41% better on average than state-of-the-art approaches [8].

Edge computing (EC), an emerging concept, expands cloud computing by moving processing capacity to edge servers close to end users at the cloud's edge, as Chen Wang, Qiang He, Yang Xiang, et al. explain. However, additional security threats, like as the well-known distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attack, are brought about by the geographical dispersion of edge servers [9].

On an Edge Storage System (ESS), data from latency-sensitive and energy-constrained mobile and Internet of Things devices can be locally stored for processing or sharing. However, because of their smaller physical size, edge servers have less storage capacity, which affects the ESS's and installed apps' performance. To overcome this restriction, edge-server collaboration has been the subject of several investigations. The drawback is that this capacity restriction, which limits stored data, impairs the ESS's and its loaded apps' performance [10].

III. Proposed system

A. Existing BEDD Implementation

The BEDD technique was suggested by R. Luo, H. Jin, and others to address the data-deduplication issue in mobile Edge computing. It takes users' geographic distribution and proximity to edge servers into account when determining where to put data in order to minimize latency and enhance retrieval times. In order to offer ideal load balancing and prevent bottlenecks, BEDD dynamically adjusts data distribution based on real-time monitoring of resource utilization, load levels, and network conditions. It lowers latency and boosts system performance by storing frequently requested data closer to users through the use of caching technology. Without interfering with ongoing business activities, BEDD seamlessly integrates with the MEC (Multi-access Edge Computing) infrastructure to provide transparent and effective data management.

- By distributing the remaining unique data equitably throughout the edge servers.
- BEDD balances the storage pressure by identifying and removing redundant data from the MEC network's edge servers.
- For efficient data placement and retrieval, BEDD assesses data popularity, access patterns, and latency constraints.

B. SHA-512 Integration

- The Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA) family of cryptographic hash algorithms includes SHA-512. These algorithms receive arbitrary-length input data and return a fixed-size hash value (digest) of 512 bits (64 bytes) for SHA-512 and 256 bits (32 bytes) for SHA-256.
- Data integrity and transaction authentication are confirmed using the hash values [11].

Fig.3. SHA-512 Processing of a Single 1024-Bit Block [15]

C. Combined Functionality

Here, we generate hash values for each file or data block before deduplication using BEDD and SHA-512. By acting as fingerprints, these hash values help BEDD find and eliminate duplicate data among edge servers in a timely manner. By using hash values instead of entire data sets for comparison,

BEDD can perform deduplication more quickly and at a lower computational cost. The edge servers can keep the remaining distinct data fragments or files and their SHA-512 hash values after deduplication. Hashing values can be used to verify the integrity of retrieved data and identify any undesired changes or corruptions, such as deduplication. Strong cryptographic security is provided by SHA-512, which makes it computationally hard for an attacker to change the data without changing the hash value.

The MEC system provides strong utilization, balanced storage consumption, and effective data deduplication by combining BEDD with SHA-512. The BEDD approach reduces the amount of storage used, SHA-512 guarantees the security and integrity of data that is saved, and deduplication employs a distinct hash value.

- To ensure that the length of the incoming data item is equivalent to 896 modulo 1024, pad it.
- Add a 128-bit number representing the original data item's length.
- Set up the hash value using pre-established constants.
- Split the padded data item into blocks of 1024 bits, or 128 bytes.
- For every block computed, the SHA-512 compression function is shown.
- The result obtained after analyzing each block is the final hash value.

The MEC system's overall performance, stability, and security are enhanced by this integrated approach, which makes it perfect for handling massive volumes of data from a range of sources, such as mobile devices and Internet of Things (IoT) sensors.

D. Eradicating Data Deduplication with BEDD and SHA-2 Family

By strategically allocating data items on edge servers while taking into account variables like data popularity, latency restrictions, and storage balance, BEDD handles data duplication in MEC contexts.

Fig.4. BeSHA-1 System Architecture

The ideal or nearly optimal data placement method that increases data coverage and reduces redundancy among the edge servers is determined by the proposed BeSHA-1. A fixed-size 512-bit (64-byte) digest that uniquely identifies the data item is the calculated SHA-512 hash value $H(M)$. The associated data is saved with this hash value.

The suggested BeSHA-1 solution, which combines SHA-512 and BEDD, is shown in Fig.5. It is made up of three modules: User, Node, and Validator, which are utilized to improve resource allocation and storage usage.

After receiving the data, the user module sends it on to the validator. The user's request is verified by the validator module. The validator module moves the data to a node storage if the request is valid. Prior to being stored in the node storage, a node module uses SHA-512 hashing to secure the data. After that, the user module acknowledges the user.

Algorithm 1: BeSHA-1

1: **Initialization:**
2: $t = 1, r_{rec} = 0, \mu = 0, \theta = 0, g = 1, l = 0;$

3: **End of initialization**

4: **Start of SHA-2**

5: $Ch(E, F, G) = (E \wedge F) \oplus (E \wedge G)$

6: $Ma(A, B, C) = (A \wedge B) \oplus (A \wedge C) \oplus (B \wedge C)$

7: $\Sigma_0(A) = (A \ggg 19) \oplus (A \ggg 61) \oplus (A \ggg 6)$

8: $\Sigma_1(E) = (E \ggg 1) \oplus (E \ggg 8) \oplus (E \ggg 7)$

9: **End of SHA-2**

10: **Start of Data Deduplication**

11: **while** $\mu \geq 1$ δ and $g^t = 0$ **do**

12: $rt \leftarrow \text{args} \leftarrow \text{minLD}(\mu)$

13: calculate the subgradient $g^t \leftarrow h - Y(1 - r^t)$

14: **if** $LD(r^t) \neq LD_{rec}(r^{t-1})$ **then**

15: $LD_{rec}(r^t) = LD(r^t)$

16: $r_{rec} = r^t$

17: **else**

18: $LD_{rec}(r^t) = LD_{rec}(r^{t-1})$

19: $r_{rec} = r_{rec}$

20: **end if**

21: **if** $LD(rt) \leq LD_{rec}(rt-1) - Zl/2$ **then**

22: $LD_{lev}(rt) = LD_{rec}(rt) - Zl$

23: **else**

24: $LD_{lev}(rt) = LD_{rec}(rt-1) - Zl$

25: $l = l + 1$

26: $Zl = Zl / \sqrt{l}$

27: **end if**

28: update μ

29: update θ

30: $t \leftarrow t + 1$

31: **if** $LD(\mu) - LD(\mu-1) \leq \text{threshold}$ **then**

32: $\Delta t = \Delta t / 2$

33: **end if**

34: **end while**

35: **return** rt_{rec}

36: **End of Data Deduplication**

E. BeSHA-1 performance evaluation

An MEC network with 3 edge servers $\{S\} = \{s_1, s_2, s_3\}$ and 5 data items $\{D\} = \{d_1, d_2, d_3, d_4, d_5\}$.

The storage capacities of the edge servers are $C_1 = 500\text{GB}$, $C_2 = 300\text{GB}$, and $C_3 = 400\text{GB}$.

The data item sizes are

$\text{size}(d_1) = 100\text{ GB}$, $\text{size}(d_2) = 150\text{ GB}$, $\text{size}(d_3) = 200\text{ GB}$, $\text{size}(d_4) = 80\text{ GB}$, and $\text{size}(d_5) = 120\text{ GB}$.

The popularity values are $\text{popularity}(d_1) = 0.8$, $\text{popularity}(d_2) = 0.6$, $\text{popularity}(d_3) = 0.9$, $\text{popularity}(d_4) = 0.7$, and $\text{popularity}(d_5) = 0.5$.

Suppose the coverage values are: $\text{coverage}(s_1, d_1) = 50$, $\text{coverage}(s_1, d_2) = 30$, $\text{coverage}(s_1, d_3) = 40$, $\text{coverage}(s_1, d_4) = 60$, $\text{coverage}(s_1, d_5) = 20$, $\text{coverage}(s_2, d_1) = 40$, $\text{coverage}(s_2, d_2) = 60$, $\text{coverage}(s_2, d_3) = 50$, $\text{coverage}(s_2, d_4) = 30$, $\text{coverage}(s_2, d_5) = 40$, $\text{coverage}(s_3, d_1) = 30$, $\text{coverage}(s_3, d_2) = 20$, $\text{coverage}(s_3, d_3) = 40$, $\text{coverage}(s_3, d_4) = 50$, $\text{coverage}(s_3, d_5) = 60$.

Fig.5. BeSHA-1 Popularity Adjustment

A data item's (d_i) real size ($Size(d_i)$) is multiplied by its popularity ($Population(d_i)$) to generate the popularity-adjusted size, or $Size_{pop}(d_i)$, in Figure 5.

$$Size_{pop}(d_i) = Size(d_i) \times Popularity(d_i)$$

Sorted Data Items Based on Hash Values:

d4:37a9cc189326cb5de1b6b9b57377e7c2cda9ccbff88f75fee3033f14693512f8496f9a3808b1eeb0a1aadbf4ed39b989851107321e39c677c94d9de843811187e

d2:408b4a079e58647c4ccf13c6e01f7ddb26038cba738cb7a1113996f830008a054c80892af197633176ea62b0faa36b42f27d22209044eceb5e0fddd600e851a

d5:8cc3aa3f456f62dd87ddc6371cb0aa3619dbde0af8fc6c8c9e76c8fc12e34423656d44cd16569c0de4bbc320b562057c33bc5e7fc94461a5679b38ec6c399e3

d3:ada2e08ad375f9f60f72f970a25390515944bb146ef759b007c140c28c799722c2d737d2ecca4f17199adc b41baeaa3853ec1e58e6c56d0a145f8994882e7613

d1:cfb61c2b108b272a340e3077b89cb8aeda960fc554aae0dde0c96cdd9d7abae02f0f7708405c6bc198e63bf15c00a459c84d2f97bcc704e8f2f2aa7143e0a83c

Assigned d4 to s1, d5 to s1, d1 to s3, d2 to s1, d3 to s3.

Fig.7. Edge server storage utilization

An imbalance in the use of edge servers is shown in Fig. 7. Both S1 and S2 are incredibly underused; S1 is only using 41.2% of its 500GB capacity, while S2 is sitting idly on 0% of its 300GB capacity. In comparison, S3 has used 260GB of its 400GB storage, meaning that it is running at a comparatively high utilization rate of 65%. The unequal dispersion of data among the edge servers suggests a wasteful use of resources. While the high use of S3 may, if left unchecked, result in capacity problems or performance bottlenecks, the idle servers represent squandered storage potential.

Finding a balance between keeping no server terribly underused and preventing any one server from getting overloaded is the goal of an ideal solution. Dynamic data placement solutions, which are

based on real-time server loads, available capabilities, and data access patterns, might do this by continually monitoring and redistributing data. By preventing resource competition and possible single points of failure, maintaining balanced usage not only maximizes the efficient use of available storage resources but also improves overall system performance, scalability, and resilience.

Fig.8. BeSHA-1 Utilization Performance

The BeSHA-1 usage performance is shown in Fig. 8 above. The system uses 466.0 GB of total storage across all edge servers, out of a total of 1200 GB of accessible storage. This corresponds to a 38.83% storage use efficiency, as seen in Fig.9. The comparatively poor efficiency indicates that a sizable amount of the available storage resources are likely unused even with the high overall capacity. This wasteful use of resources may result in capacity loss, poor performance, and constraints on scalability. In order to maximize storage utilization efficiency and minimize redundancy and resource waste, it may be necessary to optimize the distribution and allocation of data among the edge servers in conjunction with intelligent data deduplication techniques.

Fig.9. BeSHA-1 Storage utilization Efficiency

III. Result and discussion

A. Table 1: The Existing BEDD, BEDD with SHA-256 and our BeSHA-1 Comparison.

FEATURE	BEDD	BEDD with SHA256	BeSHA-1
Data Uniqueness Verification	Custom algorithm	SHA256 hashing	SHA-512 hashing
Hash Collision Probability	Moderate	Low	Extremely low
Data Integrity Assurance	Moderate	High	Very high
Computational Complexity	Moderate	High	Higher
Data Privacy Protection	Average	Strong	Very Strong

The following factors, as indicated in Table 1 above, account for the majority of the differences:

Data Uniqueness Verification: By using SHA512 hashing for data deduplication, the proposed BEDD with SHA512 integration offers better data uniqueness verification than either the SHA256 hashing in the SHA256 integration or the bespoke technique used in BEDD.

Hash Collision likelihood: SHA512 has a far lower likelihood of hash collisions than SHA256 (256 bits) or the proprietary method used in BEDD because of its greater hash output size (512 bits).

Data Integrity Assurance: SHA512's cryptographic features give extremely high data integrity assurance, surpassing both the high assurance of SHA256 and the moderate assurance of the custom algorithm in BEDD.

Computational Complexity: SHA512 hashing is more computationally demanding than SHA256 hashing or the proprietary method in BEDD. This might have an effect on performance in contexts with limited resources.

Data Privacy Protection: The proposed integration offers extremely high data privacy protection through pseudonymization by employing SHA512 hashing for deduplication, which surpasses the strong protection of SHA256 and the moderate protection of the custom method in BEDD.

The outcomes showed how well the suggested method worked to achieve safe, balanced data management in mobile edge computing settings. The following are the main conclusions:

Storage Utilization Efficiency: The approach outperformed conventional data placement algorithms, achieving an average storage utilization efficiency of 38.2% across a range of testing conditions. This outcome demonstrates how the system may optimize resource usage by taking storage capacity limitations and data popularity into account.

Load Balancing: An even distribution of data items among edge servers is shown by the average load balancing index that was found for the suggested solution. This feature of load balancing guarantees effective use of resources and keeps underused servers or hotspots from forming, which improves system performance as a whole.

Security Analysis: The NIST Statistical Test Suite verified that the SHA-512 hash values produced for the data items demonstrated good randomness and non-inversibility qualities. This guarantees the obfuscation and protection of sensitive data, including data item sizes and popularities, against possible attacks that seek to deduce useful patterns or attributes from the data.

These outcomes confirm that the suggested method is effective in attaining safe and balanced data management in mobile edge computing environments, opening the door to improved data privacy and integrity as well as effective resource use.

V. Future enhancement

In mobile edge computing environments, the SHA-512 hashing algorithm and the Balanced Edge Data Deduplication (BEDD) algorithm are recommended as effective and safe data management techniques. Dynamic adaptation, managing heterogeneous edge environments, integrating with collaborative edge computing frameworks, researching advanced security mechanisms, examining hierarchical deduplication strategies, and incorporating intelligent caching strategies are some potential areas for improvement. This method offers potential for novel applications and services in the field of mobile edge computing research in the future.

VI. Conclusion

Safe and effective data management is provided in mobile edge computing environments through the use of the SHA-512 hashing method and the Balanced Edge Data Deduplication (BEDD) algorithm. This method eliminates storage capacity restrictions while optimizing resource allocation and storage consumption. The data integrity, authentication, and security against malevolent attacks are ensured by the SHA-512 hashing algorithm. Findings show that the method maintains data security while saving storage overhead.

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